

Coupling of the micro and macro flame structures in aluminum-steam suspensions based on an Euler-Lagrangian modeling approach

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Abstract

Aluminum can serve as a carbon-free energy carrier suitable for transport and storage, releasing energy as heat and hydrogen during combustion in steam. This requires a detailed understanding of the macro- and microscopic flame structures that govern aluminum particle combustion and oxide nanoparticle formation and transport. While advancements have been made in the fields of sophisticated boundary layer resolved single particle simulations and large scale flame simulations using simplified particle models, the coupling between the scales remains insufficiently understood.

In this work, a combined simulation approach is presented for macroscopic flame propagation in aluminum-steam suspensions, with the Lagrangian particle model including an improved mechanistic two-diffusion-layer formulation of the structure and transport in the micro-flames which envelope each individually burning aluminum particle. In contrast to previous approaches, the model relaxes the unity Lewis assumption. This leads to a more accurate expression for the flame standoff ratio, informed by the mixture-averaged diffusion model. Validation relies on heuristic combustion time correlations and experimental data for the standoff ratio for particles between $20\ \mu\text{m}$ and $500\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter in steam, diluted with up to 50% mole nitrogen or hydrogen.

The flame simulations provide first estimates for the reaction front propagation speed in monodisperse ($20\ \mu\text{m}$ particle diameter) aluminum steam-suspensions for equivalence ratios between 0.5 and 1.3. The simulation results show the link between the micro-flames around individual particles and macroscopic flame propagation along the particle suspension. By shifting the macroscopic conditions from lean to rich, qualitatively different flame structures are achieved, altering both single particle evolutions and macroscopic flame profiles in a coupled manner. These insights demonstrate the need to include and combine the processes from different scales in numerical simulations, especially in complex macroscopic configurations.

Keywords: Multiscale, Diffusion flame, Metal fuels, Reaction front speed, Particles

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1 Introduction

To realize the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of “clean and affordable energy” [1], energy carriers suitable for long-term storage and long-distance transport are essential. In this context, metals have been proposed as carbon-free chemical energy carriers due to their potential to establish a circular energy economy [2, 3].

Among the proposed metal-based energy carriers, aluminum stands out as a particularly promising candidate [4]. It offers several advantages over other metals, most notably an exceptionally high energy density [2, 3, 5]. When combusted in pure steam (H_2O), aluminum releases

approximately half of its stored energy as hydrogen, while the remainder is converted into high-temperature heat. This dual energy output makes it a complement for long term storage and long distance transport within a hydrogen-based energy economy [2, 6].

A major challenge lies in the formation of undesirable nanometer-sized aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) particles during the combustion [5]. A fraction of the nanoparticles re-deposit on the micrometer sized "mother" particle, while the remainder spreads in the bulk gas [7, 8]. This dispersion introduces significant challenges for industrial implementation, necessitating additional filtration and recycling steps. A detailed understanding of nanoparticle formation and deposition at the microscale is therefore essential. The exact split of aluminum oxide being deposited and spread strongly depends on the local combustion conditions [7, 8], which are bidirectionally coupled to both the particle evolutions and macroscopic flame configuration [9]. Yet such understanding remains incomplete. Advancing this knowledge can inform the development of smart burner designs, minimizing or even preventing nanoparticle formation from the start.

The combustion of aluminum has been studied in the context of solid propellant rocket engines, where aluminum is used as an additive [5]. In this application, nanometer-sized aluminum particles (below 100 nm diameter) are chosen to achieve the high required heat release rates. The particles are burnt in the post-flame-region of the solid propellant, within a complex mixture of gases and oxidizers, including O_2 , H_2O , CO_2 , CO , and others. Numerous experiments have been conducted on the combustion of individually burning aluminum particles across a range of particle sizes and gas compositions, see e.g., [10, 11, 12, 13]. The main observable of these experiments remains the combustion time together with the phenomenology of the particle combustion. The resulting data has formed the basis for widely used heuristic correlations that relate combustion time to oxidizer availability, bulk gas temperature and pressure, and particle size [10, 14]. Such correlations nowadays serve as a standard reference for evaluating aluminum particle combustion times.

The combustion of micrometer sized aluminum particles in pure or nitrogenated steam, while comparatively less explored, is attracting growing interest due to its potential in energy applications [2, 14, 15, 16]. In general, aluminum particles are expected to burn in a homogeneous combustion mode, fulfilling the Glasman criterion [17]. Hence, a characteristic feature of aluminum combustion across a wide range of oxidizers is the formation of a thin, detached micro-diffusion flame sheet that surrounds the burning particle [11, 12, 18]. Especially in a steam environment, the micro-diffusion-flame resides in close proximity to the particle (within 1.5 particle diameters). Depending on the combustion environment, the flame can approach the particle surface closely enough to facilitate heterogeneous reactions directly at the particle surface [19, 20]. This regime transition is of special interest in order to promote deposition of Al_2O_3 on the particle and avoid the formation of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in the bulk. Another distinctive feature of the combustion in steam is the formation of one or more pronounced aluminum oxide "lobes" or "caps" which grow on the parent aluminum particle [14]. These structures cover some of the reactive surface, and interfere with the gas transport around the particle, ultimately leading to asymmetric combustion and intermittent disruptive events [14, 21, 22].

Numerical simulations offer valuable insights into the flame's micro-structure and the behavior of burning aluminum particles in steam. Hence, the focus of many recent numerical works is set on the analysis of the micro-diffusion-flame and the yet partially understood nanoparticle dynamics therein. Recently, boundary layer resolved simulations have been increasingly utilized by researchers to explore the different physical processes which govern the nanoparticle behavior, such as thermophoresis, nucleation, or agglomeration. [7, 8, 19, 23, 24]

When an aluminum-air/steam flame is stabilized in a group combustion scenario, e.g., in a Bunsen or counterflow burner, an additional scale is added to the setup. The previously described microscopic combustion phenomena appear around every involved individual particle. As schematically shown in Fig. 1, many micro-diffusion flames coexist. Additionally, on the macroscopic scale, a reaction front propagates through the suspension which marks the leading edge where individual particles have ignited and formed micro-diffusion flames.

Figure 1: Schematic of a Al-Steam flame simulation setup, including both the macroscopic propagation of the reaction front (resolved) and the microscopic diffusion flames which surround each particle (mechanistic point-particle description).

Simulations of macroscopic flame propagation in aluminum-air/steam suspensions are helpful to design aluminum burners and, perspective, semi-industrial demonstrators and facilities for aluminum combustion. For such simulations, computationally very efficient point-particle models are required, such that boundary layer resolved particle models are not suitable. Instead, most available models for large scale simulations are traditionally based on common droplet evaporation models known from spray combustion [17, 25]. In spray combustion, the fuel diffuses through the diffusion-boundary layer of the particle and reacts far from the particle surface. The micro-diffusion flames are often not represented in the simulations. The reaction is modeled by a homogeneous reaction rate in the Eulerian model of the bulk gas, applying Arrhenius-type correlations for the kinetically controlled rate. Recently, Sewerin and Finke [26] extended this approach to also include the transition to the heterogeneous combustion mode.

For aluminum combustion with a homogeneous flame near the particle surface, evaporation models need to be adapted to consider the influence of the micro-flame sheet which is sustained by diffusive fluxes of fuel and oxidizer from both sides of the micro-flame. To reduce the number of required differential equations and obtain single particle models suitable for the macroscopic flame simulations, the B-equation approach [17, 27] is widely used. In this approach, two out of three conservation equations (fuel, oxidizer, heat) for the micro-flame are combined. This procedure homogenizes the differential equation system, inserting expressions for the ratio between the inhomogeneous terms, based on stoichiometry and the heat of evaporation [17, 27]. The entirety of the micro-flame with both diffusion layers is then described by a single, continuous differential equation. DesJardin *et al.* [27] included Al_2O_3 as fourth equation into the B-equation coupling by approximating it as a diffusing gas phase, obtaining a deposition rate. Zhang *et al.* presented a detailed single particle model based on the B-equation approach and applied it to simulations of several macroscopic flame types [28, 29]. A key limitation of the B-equation approach lies in the underlying assumptions it requires, most importantly unity Lewis numbers and a single set of averaged thermodynamic properties for all diffusion layers, as well as the assumption that evaporation is solely limited by heat transfer.

Other authors reported more detailed point particle models, explicitly taking into account two or more diffusion layers on both sides of the micro-diffusion-flame. Instead of introducing the relation between heat and mass flow, both diffusion layers are solved distinctly and matched at the interfaces. Examples of early analytical models for homogeneous metal combustion, which do include two diffusion layers have been presented by Brzustowski and Glassmann [30] and Law [25], who studied combustion times, and single particle combustion regimes. Law [25] included a model for the transport of oxide nanoparticles based on the assumption that they follow the convective flow perfectly. This assumption lead to the conclusion that nanoparticles are always transported away from aluminum particles burning in air, and never deposited. [25].

Still, lobe formation and growth during combustion in air has been experimentally observed [13]. King [31] presented a three-layer model that also incorporates the dissociation of Al_2O_3 into gaseous suboxides in the flame sheet and their condensation to Al_2O_3 in a distinct condensation layer. While the multi-diffusion-layer approach in general allows to distinct diffusion coefficients of aluminum and oxidizer, the authors kept the unity Lewis assumption in order to obtain analytical solutions. Also, the works concentrated exclusively on single particle combustion.

More broadly, research on aluminum combustion has largely followed two distinct paths: The field of sophisticated single particle simulations with focus on the micro-diffusion-flame structure on one side, and the field of macroscopic flame simulations based on adapted spray droplet models with focus on integrated quantities such as reaction front speeds in aluminum-air suspensions on the other side. Despite advances in both areas, the coupling between the micro-scale flame characteristics, including nanoparticle deposition, and the global flame behavior remains insufficiently understood.

To address this gap, the present work aims to bridge micro- and macro-scale combustion phenomena by simulating macroscopic flames in aluminum–steam suspensions, combined with an extended Lagrangian point-particle model which incorporates a mechanistic representation of the micro-diffusion flame structure. Specifically, it features two diffusion layers surrounding each particle, building upon the classical analytical approaches [25, 30], as detailed in Sec. 2. In contrast to the commonly applied unity-Lewis number assumption, the improved model employs a mixture-averaged diffusion formulation to separately evaluate the transport of aluminum and steam towards the flame. This refinement allows for a more consistent estimation of the flame standoff ratio, offering an improvement over traditional two-layer and B-equation approaches. Compared to boundary layer resolved simulations, the mechanistic approach in the particle model maintains its numerical efficiency, aimed to be used in large scale CFD simulations. Model validation is carried out in Sec. 3 by comparing predicted combustion times and flame standoff ratios against experimental data from single-particle combustion. A detailed analysis of the coupled microscopic and macroscopic flame structures in aluminum–steam suspensions is presented in Sec. 4. The different combustion phases on single particle level and flame zones on macroscopic level are evaluated for lean and rich flames, representing an exemplary change of the macroscopic configuration.

2 Single Particle Model

Particles in the Euler-Lagrangian context are considered point-particles, described by the Lagrangian particle-in-cell model, without a resolved geometry or extent. Still, a 3-dimensional concept of a burning aluminum particle, which burns with a detached diffusion flame, forms the basis to derive expressions for the mass and heat transfer rates in this section, providing the point-sources for the Euler-Lagrangian simulations for a single aluminum particle.

Given the high particle temperatures (above 2350 K), gas phase chemical kinetics are expected to be fast compared to diffusion of fuel and oxidizer and kinetics are thus assumed not to be the rate limiting step. Therefore, fuel and oxidizer are considered to react at the rate at which they are mixed. It should be noted that short-lived sub-oxides such as AlO have been experimentally observed in the particle boundary layer [11]. This indicates that the aluminum combustion takes intermediate steps, which have been extensively investigated for the reaction with air [11, 23, 32, 33]. Differently, the chemistry of aluminum combustion with H_2O is a subject of ongoing research [19, 34], which can only draw on very limited quantitative experimental reference data [23, 33]. Reaction rates and pathways of aluminum combustion in water to date remain mainly numerically investigated and vary significantly dependent on the chosen reference [33]. Thus, the presented modeling approach approximates the aluminum combustion by a single step reaction forming Al_2O_3 , similar to previous models from literature [17, 25, 30].

It is further generally agreed that, if the temperature reaches the value of 4000 K, Al_2O_3 becomes unstable and splits up into the gaseous species AlO and AlO_2 , which is an endothermic reaction, limiting the temperature of the flame [5, 17, 25, 35]. Further away from the flame, at

lower temperatures, the gaseous oxides would exothermically re-condense to Al_2O_3 . In an *a-posteriori* validation, flame temperatures obtained in this work are shown to stay below 3950 K, see Secs. 3 and 4, such that dissociation is expected to have a minor impact and thus is considered negligible.

With these assumptions, the flame surrounding the particle is described by the Burke-Schumann limit for an infinitely thin flame sheet (see e.g. [17]), as indicated by the orange line in Fig. 2. This approach, with its clearly stated assumptions, is not affected by potential issues such as boundary-layer resolution or dependencies on the numerical discretization. While not the primary motivation here, it also lends itself well to implementation in CFD frameworks.

Heterogeneous surface reactions have been hypothesized to contribute to the heat release in cold environments or at particle diameters below $10\ \mu\text{m}$ [5, 14, 19, 20], and are not covered in this work: During the combustion of micrometer-sized particles in hot steam within macroscopic flames, the particles are expected to burn entirely in the homogeneous regime.

The geometric model for the particle composed of aluminum and oxide in solid and fully molten state is described in Sec. 2.1. The mass and heat transport in the region around the particle and the flame are described in Sec. 2.2 and 2.3, respectively. Section. 2.4, provides closure terms for densities and vapor pressures.

2.1 Particle Geometry

Figure 2: The geometry of a single molten aluminum particle, featuring an aluminum oxide spherical cap and a homogeneous flame with low standoff ratio.

The particle is composed of aluminum and aluminum oxide in solid and/or liquid form. Below the melting temperature of Al_2O_3 , the solid aluminum oxide is assumed to form a passivating layer that covers the aluminum in a spherical core-shell structure. In the solid state, the particle is inert and only exchanges heat with the gas phase, no mass is exchanged. The heat transfer is modeled as described in Sec. 2.3, treating the entire, spherical, passivated particle as oxide sphere with the outer radius

$$r_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi} (V_{\text{Al}} + V_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}) \right)^{1/3}. \quad (1)$$

The volumes V_i are given by the mass m_i and the density ρ_i by $V_i = m_i/\rho_i$ with $i = \text{Al}, \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. When the oxide melts, the oxide layer contracts to a single oxide cap and a structure composed of two spherical caps is formed, as shown in Fig. 2. The geometry of the spherical caps is determined by the contact angle of the two surfaces and by the volumes V_i , now forming the liquid caps. The geometry of the fully molten particle as defined in Fig. 2, i.e., the radii of

both the aluminum and oxide cap are then achieved by solving the following algebraic equation system:

$$\sum_{i=\text{Al,Al}_2\text{O}_3} \vartheta_i = 90^\circ \quad (2)$$

$$\sin(\vartheta_i) r_i = h \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\pi r_i^3}{3} (2 + \cos \vartheta_i)(1 - \cos \vartheta_i)^2 = V_i. \quad (4)$$

Note that a contact angle of 90° between liquid Al and liquid Al_2O_3 is a common assumption [28, 29], which may not be accurate. The influence of the oxide cap is expected to become significant towards the end of the combustion process, as larger portions of the particle surface become covered. In contrast, its impact is assumed to be small during the early stages of combustion.

2.2 Mass Transport and Flame Standoff Ratio

The region around the particle and the flame is not resolved. Instead, the boundary layer is characterized by the states at the three distinctive, spherical sheets: The particle surface (subscript s), the flame sheet (subscript f) and the bulk gas or far field (subscript g). Between these sheets, two non-reactive diffusion layers are located: The inner diffusion layer between particle and flame (denoted ‘1’) and the outer diffusion layer between flame and bulk (denoted ‘2’). The labeling and subscripts are indicated in the lower right in Fig. 2.

To obtain an expression for the mass transport rates and the flame radius, the mass conservation equation is solved for each of the diffusion layers separately and the boundary conditions of both solutions at the flame sheet are matched [25, 30].

In both of the spherical, rotational-symmetric diffusion layers ‘1’ and ‘2’, the species mass conservation equation must hold for every gaseous species i (transported and non-transported species) in radial direction r [17]:

$$\dot{m}_{1|2} Y_i = 4\pi r^2 \rho D_i \frac{dY_i}{dr} + \dot{m}_i. \quad (5)$$

Here, Y_i denotes the mass fraction of species i and $\dot{m}_{1|2} = 4\pi r^2 \rho u$ is the total mass flow of gas in the diffusion layer, excluding Al_2O_3 which exists in the form of condensed nanoparticles and does not diffuse [25]. The net mass flow \dot{m}_i of species i appears as inhomogeneous term after integrating $\rho u \nabla Y_i = \rho D_i \nabla^2 Y_i$ once [17]. The relations between all mass flows are fixed by stoichiometry based on the single-step reaction given in Eqs. (6-9). Note that all mass flows are in positive r direction by definition.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} = -\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 9\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2} = 9/17 \dot{m}_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}, \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{m}_1 = \dot{m}_{\text{Al}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{m}_2 = \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2} - \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}. \quad (9)$$

All thermodynamic properties of the diffusion layers, here the density ρ and diffusion coefficients D , are evaluated for each of the layers at a reference temperature and composition obtained from the 1/3rd rule: $T_1 = 2/3T_s + 1/3T_f$ and $Y_{i,1} = 2/3Y_{i,s} + 1/3Y_{i,f}$ for layer ‘1’. Layer ‘2’ is treated equally, i.e., $T_2 = 2/3T_f + 1/3T_g$. The mixture-averaged diffusion model is used to calculate the diffusion coefficients using Cantera [36].

The solution of Eq. (5) for diffusion layer ‘1’ and $i = \text{Al}$ with the boundary conditions $Y_{\text{Al}}(r = r_{\text{Al}}) = Y_{\text{Al},s}$ and $Y_{\text{Al}}(r = r_f) = 0$ leads to the conventional Sherwood correlation for

spheres and definition of the mass transport number B [17] with an additional term which represents the finite distance of the flame from the particle [30]:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} = 4\pi r_{\text{Al}} \rho_1 D_{1,\text{Al}} \frac{r_f}{r_f - r_{\text{Al}}} \ln(1 + B_{\text{Al}}), \quad (10)$$

$$B_{\text{Al}} = \frac{Y_{\text{Al},s} - Y_{\text{Al},f}}{1 - Y_{\text{Al},s}} = \frac{Y_{\text{Al},s}}{1 - Y_{\text{Al},s}}. \quad (11)$$

The flame radius r_f is not yet known at this point and must be obtained from solving Eq. (5) for diffusion layer ‘2’ with $i = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(r = r_f) = 0$ and $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(r \rightarrow \infty) = Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O},g}$

$$\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} = \frac{9}{2} \pi r_f \rho_2 D_{2,\text{H}_2\text{O}} \ln(1 + B_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}), \quad (12)$$

$$B_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O},f} - Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O},g}}{9/8 - Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O},f}} = -\frac{8}{9} Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O},g}. \quad (13)$$

Convection improves the mass and heat transfer between particle and bulk, which commonly is taken into account by a Sherwood expression, correcting the transfer rates for increasing particle Reynolds numbers, see e.g. [17]. This is implicitly neglected here, as the second boundary condition is applied infinitely far away from the particle ($r \rightarrow \infty$). For highly convective environments, such as highly turbulent flames, the effect of convection can be added to the presented model in the future by adjusting the boundary condition. However, in the single particle and laminar flame setups within this work, particle Reynolds numbers are generally low and convection is considered negligible. The highest particle Reynolds number throughout all presented calculations is reached in the inert preheating-zone of the stoichiometric ($\phi = 1$) aluminum-steam flame in Sec. 4, reaching 0.084, while for a reacting particle the maximum reached value is 0.026.

Using the fixed ratio between the aluminum and steam mass flow from Eq. (7), an expression for the flame radius and standoff ratio (FSR) is obtained

$$\text{FSR} = \frac{r_f}{r_{\text{Al}}} = 1 - \frac{8}{9} \frac{\rho_1 D_{1,\text{Al}}}{\rho_2 D_{2,\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \frac{\ln(1 + B_{\text{Al}})}{\ln(1 + B_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})}. \quad (14)$$

Note that $\text{FSR} \geq 1$ since $\ln(1 + B_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) \leq 0$. Inserting Eq. (14) into (12) provides an expression for the combustion rate, which is composed of two parts. These parts have the form of diffusion rates and, if examined separately, are recognizable as conventional Sherwood correlations for spheres (corrected for the Stefan flow and stoichiometry), known from other particle/droplet combustion configurations:

1. The **evaporative component** describes the evaporation rate of a particle with $\text{FSR} \rightarrow \infty$.
2. The **heterogeneous component** describes the fuel consumption rate of a heterogeneously burning particle, limited by the diffusion on incoming oxidizer with $\text{FSR} = 1$

$$\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} = \underbrace{4\pi r_{\text{Al}} \rho_1 D_{1,\text{Al}} \ln(1 + B_{\text{Al}})}_{\text{evaporative component}} - \underbrace{\frac{9}{2} \pi r_{\text{Al}} \rho_2 D_{2,\text{H}_2\text{O}} \ln(1 + B_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})}_{\text{heterogeneous component}}. \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) shows that these two rates have to be summed up to obtain the reaction rate of a homogeneously burning particle with finite FSR. This provides valuable insights into the relation between the consumption rates of particle that evaporate, react heterogeneously or burn with a nearby homogeneous flame. The evaporation rate given by the ‘evaporative component’

of Eq. (15) is comparable to a ‘base’ rate of evaporation/combustion, which is controlled by the particle temperature, known from droplet/spray evaporation. The reaction rate is further increased in the case of finite flame distances due to the decreased diffusion distance between particle and flame. The increase is equivalent to the reaction rate of a heterogeneously reacting particle, and it increases with availability of oxidizer but is independent of the FSR. Both evaporative and heterogeneous component can reach zero or infinity independently, leading to the limiting cases of the homogeneous combustion as described by the present model:

- In the case of **zero oxidizer** availability, the heterogeneous component is zero, $\text{FSR} \rightarrow \infty$, and the rate converges to an evaporation model (e.g., group combustion scenario [37]).
- If **no fuel evaporates**, the evaporative component is zero, $\text{FSR} = 1$, and the particle burns entirely heterogeneously (e.g., a common assumption for iron combustion [3, 38]).
- In the case of **100% oxidizer**, the heterogeneous component approaches infinity while $\text{FSR} \rightarrow 1$.
- If the **particle reaches boiling temperature**, the evaporative component approaches infinity with $\text{FSR} \rightarrow \infty$

Up to this point, a perfect spherical geometry has been the premise for the formulation and solution of the one-dimensional equation system. Next, the influence of surface area covered by the oxide cap will be taken into account. This is done by introducing an effective surface area (e.g. [29, 31]) a_{eff} , which ranges between 0 and 1 and expresses how much surface area of a theoretical full sphere with radius r_{Al} is actually uncovered

$$a_{\text{eff}} = A_{\text{Al}}/(4\pi r_{\text{Al}}^2). \quad (16)$$

Finally, the mass change rates of the particle $dm_{p,i}/dt$ are defined in Eqs. (17-22). Therein, a scalar model parameter ξ is introduced which ranges between 0 and 100% and defines the mass ratio of oxide which is deposited on the particle. The remaining oxide is transported to the bulk gas, see also Fig. 2.

$$\frac{dm_{p,\text{Al}}}{dt} = -\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}}, \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{dm_{p,\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}}{dt} = \xi \frac{17}{9} \dot{m}_{\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}}, \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{m}_{t,\text{Al}} = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$\dot{m}_{t,\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = (1 - \xi) \frac{17}{9} \dot{m}_{\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}}, \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{m}_{t,\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}}, \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{m}_{t,\text{H}_2} = \frac{1}{9} \dot{m}_{\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}}. \quad (22)$$

The mass transfer rates $\dot{m}_{t,i}$ from the particle system to the bulk gas appear as source terms in the governing equations in the Eulerian description of the gas phase, see Sec. 2.4 and [9] for details. A special case arises if no oxidizer is available in the bulk gas and the particle enters the pure evaporation edge case. With evaporation ongoing, \dot{m}_{Al} will still take a finite value, according to Eq. (10 and 15). The oxidizer consumption rate is bound to that value by stoichiometry, according to Eq. 21. Consequently, a finite sink term would be applied to the gas phase despite no oxidizer is available, leading to unphysical results. To prevent this, a distinction has to be made, switching explicitly from combustion (release of Al_2O_3 and H_2 into the bulk gas, consumption of H_2O) to evaporation (release of Al into the bulk gas).

if ($Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O},g} = 0$):

$$\frac{dm_{p,\text{Al}}}{dt} = -\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}} = -\dot{m}_{t,\text{Al}} a_{\text{eff}}, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{dm_{p,\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}}{dt} = 0, \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{m}_{t,\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = \dot{m}_{t,\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \dot{m}_{t,\text{H}_2} = 0. \quad (25)$$

2.3 Heat Transport and Flame Temperature

In analogy to the mass transport, the heat conservation equation is solved for both diffusion layers separately and matched at the flame sheet. Ultimately, the temperature T_f of the micro-flame and the total heat transport rates \dot{h}_1 and \dot{h}_2 (see also Fig. 2) for the diffusion layers ‘1’ and ‘2’, respectively, are obtained from this procedure.

The heat conservation equation in radial direction r reads [17]

$$\sum_i \dot{m}_i c_{p,i} T = 4\pi r^2 \lambda \frac{dT}{dr} + \dot{h}_{1|2} \quad (26)$$

with i taking the values Al, H₂O, H₂, and Al₂O₃. For brevity, the symbols C and L are introduced for the convective and conductive heat transport.

$$\sum_i \dot{m}_i c_{p,i} = C, \quad (27)$$

$$4\pi r_p \lambda = L. \quad (28)$$

For both diffusion layers ‘1’ and ‘2’, Eq. (26) is separately integrated over r . Applying the boundary conditions $T_1(r = r_p) = T_p$ and $T_2(r \rightarrow \infty) = T_g$, respectively, two expressions for the flame temperature are achieved. The expressions still depend on the total heat transport rates \dot{h}_1 and \dot{h}_2

$$T_f = \left(T_p - \frac{\dot{h}_1}{C_1}\right) \exp\left(\frac{C_1}{L_1} \frac{r_f - r_p}{r_f}\right) + \frac{\dot{h}_1}{C_1}, \quad (29)$$

$$T_f = \left(T_g - \frac{\dot{h}_2}{C_2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{C_2}{L_2} \frac{-r_p}{r_f}\right) + \frac{\dot{h}_2}{C_2}. \quad (30)$$

The heat balance across the flame sheet yields a relationship between \dot{h}_1 , \dot{h}_2 , and the reaction enthalpy h_c , which is defined per unit mass of aluminum consumed. (Jkg^{-1})

$$\dot{h}_2 = \dot{h}_1 + \dot{m}_{\text{Al}} h_c. \quad (31)$$

Equations (29-31) with three unknowns can be re-arranged to obtain an explicit expression for T_f . The required thermodynamic properties, i.e., combustion enthalpy (evaluated at flame temperature), heat capacities, and thermal conductivities (evaluated for each of the layers using the 1/3-rule) are updated in every timestep for the current temperatures and compositions in the diffusion layers. Since the temperatures themselves depend on these properties, the calculation of the flame temperature numerically relies on an iterative procedure. The converged state from the last timestep is used as starting condition, such that usually after 2 iterations the flame temperature reaches a converged state within 1 K.

In the case of zero evaporation, e.g., in the case of all aluminum being consumed already, the solution of the equation system converges to the conventional Nusselt correlation for a sphere [17]:

$$\dot{h}_2(\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} = 0) = L_2(T_p - T_g) \quad (32)$$

The change rate of the particle enthalpy H_p is finally obtained as the balance of enthalpy fluxes at the particle interface

$$\frac{dH_p}{dt} = -\dot{h}_1 - \dot{h}_{\text{rad}} - \dot{h}_{\text{cap}}, \quad (33)$$

$$\dot{h}_{\text{rad}} = \epsilon \sigma A_p (T_p^4 - T_g^4), \quad (34)$$

$$\dot{h}_{\text{cap}} = \frac{A_{\text{cap}}}{r_{\text{cap}}} \lambda_{f,\text{cap}} (T_p - T_g). \quad (35)$$

with A_p the total particle surface, σ the Boltzmann constant, $\epsilon = 0.7$ the emissivity, and $\lambda_{f,\text{cap}}$ the thermal conductivity of the gas around the oxide cap, obtained from the 1/3-rule. Further, the change of the particle temperature and the enthalpy transfer to the Eulerian gas phase \dot{h}_t are direct results of the particle enthalpy rate of change. To obtain the temperature, the entire particle's enthalpy is expressed as the sum of the temperature-dependent enthalpies of all contained condensed species $i = \text{Al}, \text{Al}(l), \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(l)$, noted in Eq. (37). A numerical root finding procedure is used to invert the expression and obtain the temperature for a given enthalpy and particle composition:

$$\dot{h}_t = -\frac{dH_p}{dt} = \dot{h}_2 + \dot{h}_{\text{rad}} + \dot{h}_{\text{cap}}, \quad (36)$$

$$H_p = \sum_i m_{p,i} h_i(T_p). \quad (37)$$

2.4 Model Closure

Temperature-dependent thermodynamic properties of aluminum and aluminum oxide are obtained from the NIST database [39]. For the properties of the gaseous species, i.e., in the diffusion layers, the transport data from Glorian *et al.* [19] is used in combination with Cantera [36].

The mole fraction of aluminum at the particle surface, as a function of particle temperature, is determined using a Clausius–Clapeyron-based approach:

$$X_{\text{Al}} = \exp\left(\frac{L_v \bar{M}_{\text{Al}}}{\bar{R}} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{boil,Al}}} - \frac{1}{T_p}\right)\right). \quad (38)$$

X_{Al} is the aluminum mole fraction, $L_v = 10.898 \text{ MJkg}^{-1}$ is the latent heat of evaporation [39], \bar{M} the molar mass, \bar{R} the general gas constant, and $T_{\text{boil,Al}} = 2790 \text{ K}$ the boiling temperature of aluminum at 101325 Pa. The conversion from mole to mass fractions, as needed in the equations for the mass transport, requires the compositions at the particle surface and in the flame sheet. The compositions are obtained from the Burke-Schumann theory, following the expression $Y_i = Y_{i,s} + (Y_{i,g} - Y_{i,s})\tilde{x}$ with the mixture fraction \tilde{x} [40]. Therefore, the composition at the particle surface, including diluents, can be obtained within the iterative process which is implemented for the determination of the flame temperature.

The densities of the condensed species are calculated using polynomial expressions as listed in Tab. 1.

3 Validation

Single particle simulations are performed to validate the implemented model. Numerically obtained combustion times and flame standoff ratios for particles with different diameters and in different gas environments are compared with heuristic correlations and experimental values from literature.

Species	density in kgm^{-3}	ref.
Al	$2648 + 0.322 \frac{T}{\text{K}} - 4.99 \times 10^{-4} \frac{T^2}{\text{K}}$	[41]
Al (l)	$2553 - 0.267 \frac{T}{\text{K}}$	[41]
Al ₂ O ₃	3900	
Al ₂ O ₃ (l)	$3056 - 0.97(\frac{T}{\text{K}} - 2327)$	[7]

Table 1: Densities for solid and liquid aluminum and aluminum oxide as used in the particle model. T stands for the temperature and K for the temperature's unit Kelvin.

3.1 Combustion Times

Figure 3: Combustion times of aluminum particles in 2400 K steam at different dilution ratios (with H₂ and N₂) and particle diameters. Black lines: heuristic correlations from literature [10, 14]. Gray area/line: numerically obtained combustion times for different ratios of Al₂O₃ deposition.

The validation of the combustion times relies on the established heuristic correlations by Beckstead [10] and Halter *et al.* [14]. These correlations are based on a broad background of experimental single particle observations and measurements from the last decades, which have been motivated by the usage of aluminum as additive in solid rocket propellants [5]. With the experiments covering a wide range of oxidizer blends, gas temperatures, and particle diameters,

the correlations are capable to extrapolate their results into the combustion in hot steam, as relevant for the energy application at the center of this work.

In Fig. 3 the numerically obtained combustion times for individually burning aluminum particles steam at 2400 K are shown for different degrees of dilution and a range of particle diameters. Particles are initialized at gas temperature, covered by an initial layer of Al_2O_3 with 4 nm thickness [42, 20], which immediately contracts and forms an initial oxide cap. The particle is considered fully burnt out when all aluminum is converted to oxide, leaving only the (initial) oxide cap. The solid and dashed lines represent the reference values for the combustion time from Beckstead [10] and Halter *et al.* [14], respectively. The gray area marks the range of the numerical results, dependent on the deposition ratio ξ , which is an uncertain model parameter. The lower edge of the gray area (marked with an additional gray line) denoted the numerically obtained combustion times for zero deposition (all Al_2O_3 is transported to the bulk gas) while the upper edge represents 100% deposition (all Al_2O_3 is deposited on the particle). The numerical results show a good match with the heuristic correlations, with the correlations lying within the model uncertainty. It is apparent that deposition increases the combustion time for all atmospheres and diameters, as it decreases the amount of free aluminum surface. Since the deposition is controlled by the structure and temperature of the micro-flame [7, 8], the deposition ratio is one mechanism how the micro-structures in aluminum-steam combustion directly influence integrated quantities such as reaction front propagation speeds and flame stability.

One noticeable aspect is that the curvature of the combustion time dependent on the particle diameter is higher for the numerical results compared to the correlations. This is because the model follows a perfect d^2 law (with an additional pre-factor due to deposition), while the correlations depend on the particle diameter to the power of 1.8 (Beckstead [10]) and 1.75 (Halter *et al.* [14]).

3.2 Flame Standoff Ratios

Significantly less literature is available regarding the flame standoff ratios. Recently, Wu *et al.* [16, 22] studied aluminum particles burning in a diluted steam atmosphere without further oxidizers, using high speed color photography analysis. The hot nitrogen-diluted steam environment was produced by a flat hydrogen flame, stabilized on a ceramic honeycomb grid, and an additional central jet flame. Wu *et al.* conducted numerical simulations to characterize the burner configuration in terms of local gas temperature and composition [16], the gas state at the combustion position of the particle is provided in Tab. 2. A second operating point C2 is reported in the experimental work, but not included in this validation as it features excess oxygen in the combustion environment. They observed a very thin layer at some distance to the aluminum

	H ₂ O	N ₂	T_g
C1	55 %mole	45 %mole	2700 K

Table 2: Boundary conditions for single particle combustion at operating point C1 [22].

particle, in which alumina nanoparticles are formed and remain trapped. The nanoparticles move along that layer to the point which is averted to the external convective flow direction and eventually agglomerate and detach there from the layer. They concluded that this thin layer is the flame layer and defined the radial position of the peak in the measured luminosity from the trapped, luminous nanoparticles as criterion for the flame radius.

In the following, these experimental results are used for a validation of the flame standoff ratios obtained from Eq. (14) with the diffusion coefficients from the mixture-averaged diffusion model, as detailed in Sec. 2. To understand the effect of the unity Lewis assumption, Eq. (14) is also evaluated with the assumptions of $D_{a,\text{Al}} = D_{2,\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\rho_1 = \rho_2$, which is comparable to the analytical and B-equation approaches from literature. 50% of the Al_2O_3 is arbitrarily chosen to be deposited on the particle ($\xi = 0.5$) in the following, since experimental reports on the mass and size of micrometer sized residuals from aluminum combustion are scarce, show significant

scatter and suffer from the porosity of the residue [5]. The complete particle combustion until burnout is simulated and the median value of the FSR throughout the stable combustion phase is considered for further comparison.

The experimental reference values for the flame standoff ratio, which include five different particle diameters, are shown in Fig. 4 as dark (left) bars. The values obtained from the full model including the mixture-averaged diffusion model are shown as medium (center) bars, the light (right) bars show the values based on unity Lewis.

Figure 4: Flame standoff ratios at different particle diameters from experimental measurements [16, 22] (operating point C1, left, dark blue) and obtained from the model (right, medium and light blue, without and with unity Lewis assumption, respectively). 55 % H₂O + 45 % N₂ at 2700 K.

In the five reference cases, the difference between the experimental and numerical results stays within the range between 4% and 31%. This is a substantial improvement compared to the FSR based on unity Lewis, which show over-estimations between 32% and 83%.

Within the framework of point-particle modeling, the current formulation delivers state-of-the-art results for both combustion times and flame standoff ratios. It is therefore well suited for initial simulations of generic macroscopic flames and for detailed structural analyses.

4 Macroscopic Flame Simulations

The particle model is coupled to an in-house Euler-Lagrangian flame solver, which has previously been used to simulate reaction front propagation in iron-air suspensions [9]. In this one-dimensional stationary solver, a reaction front is stabilized at a fixed x position in the simulation domain, as shown in Fig. 1. It propagates in negative x direction and has an infinite expansion in y and z direction (i.e. $\partial/\partial y = 0$ and $\partial/\partial z = 0$). The Lagrangian particles and the Eulerian gas phase models are bi-directionally coupled via an operator splitting approach. The transfer rates for heat (\dot{h}_t) and species mass ($\dot{m}_{i,t}$) are obtained from the single particle model. The heat and mass transfer from the single particle are scaled with the particle number density to obtain volume source terms in the balance equations for heat and species [17]. Further details on the flame solver are provided in [9].

An extension to the flame model is introduced to address the transport of Al₂O₃: While there is still some discussion ongoing on whether Al₂O₃ can exist as a short-lived gaseous intermediate [32, 34], it is widely accepted that hypothetical gaseous Al₂O₃ is in general unstable [5, 17, 35] and condenses almost instantaneously by combination into liquid (Al₂O₃)_X nanoparticles [7, 11, 32, 34]. Still, in aluminum combustion simulations, Al₂O₃(*l*) nanoparticles are often treated as a quasi-gas phase, included as a species in the mechanism and formed by a zero-activation energy one-way reaction [7, 11, 27, 28]. While this assumption is traditionally accepted, a significant mass fraction of Al₂O₃(*l*) ‘gas’ can influence the transport property model

of the bulk gas. It decreases the thermal conductivity and increases the density of the gas mixture, such that the evaporation rates and micro-diffusion flame temperatures are over-estimated for single particles combusted in this environment. To avoid such an unwanted side effect, in this work, the quasi-gas assumption for Al_2O_3 is relaxed by the exclusion of Al_2O_3 from the list of gas phase species. It does thus not influence the gas phase transport properties in our model. Instead, the mass flux of Al_2O_3 is evaluated separately from the gas flow, assuming that the nanoparticles, after their release to the bulk, perfectly follow the gas phase velocity and temperature and contribute to the thermal inertia of the dispersion.

All macroscopic flame simulations use pure steam (100% H_2O) at 450 K at the inlet. A monodisperse particle size distribution is chosen with the initial diameter of $20\ \mu\text{m}$ for all particles. As variation parameter, the equivalence ratio ϕ is defined as the ratio between the stoichiometric mass flow of steam required for the mass flow of aluminum entering the domain at the inlet, and the actually available mass flow of steam at the inlet

$$\phi = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O},\text{inlet,stoich}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O},\text{inlet}}}. \quad (39)$$

4.1 Flame Propagation Speed

Figure 5: Reaction front speed u_r , maximum micro-flame temperature $T_{f,max}$, and adiabatic flame temperature T_{ad} , for macroscopic flames in aluminum particle ($20\ \mu\text{m}$)-steam suspensions (100% steam at 500 K).

Fig. 5 shows the calculated reaction front propagation speeds u_r (solid line), the adiabatic flame temperatures T_{ad} (dashed line), and the maximum reached micro-flame temperature $T_{f,max}$ for different equivalence ratios ϕ . The calculated reaction front speeds vary strongly between 15 cm/s and 35 cm/s dependent on the equivalence ratio, with the peak reaction front speed at $\phi = 1.0$. This finding is remarkably different to iron-air, flames, where similar macroscopic flame simulations predict a maximum propagation speed under slightly lean conditions [9, 38]. While experimental data for aluminum-steam suspension flames are currently unavailable, measurements of reaction front speeds in aluminum-air suspensions have been reported in the range of 20 cm/s to approximately 100 cm/s (see e.g., [43, 44, 45, 46]). These values exhibit considerable scatter, largely influenced by parameters such as oxygen concentration, equivalence ratio, particle size, inlet temperature, and burner orientation. For future validations of the reaction front speed in steam, there is the need for specific experiments with atmospheres and particle sizes relevant to the energy application.

4.2 Macroscopic Flame Structure

The micro-diffusion flames reach temperatures between 3600 K and 3950 K on the lean branch in Fig. 5, with the peak at $\phi = 0.8$. On the rich branch, the micro-diffusion flame temperatures

decrease quickly with increasing equivalence ratio, following the trend of the adiabatic flame temperature closely.

From the simulations, the one-dimensional profiles of gas phase and particle properties are obtained. Features of the macroscopic flames structure in aluminum-steam suspensions are discussed in this section. The Figs. 6 and 7 present the structures of a representative lean and a representative rich flame, respectively. The upper plots show the temperature profiles of the gas phase T_g (blue), the particle T_p (black) and the micro-diffusion flame T_f (red). The lower plots show the local mass fractions of steam $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (blue), hydrogen Y_{H_2} (red), aluminum Y_{Al} (gray), and the flame standoff ratio (black). Although the plots focus on the flame region, the actual simulation domain is sufficiently extended to ensure that the inlet and outlet boundaries do not interact with or influence the flame.

Under both lean and rich conditions, the particle heats up in the pre-heating zone. The melting of the aluminum is clearly visible as a plateau in the particle temperature. In the pre-heating phase, the particle temperature stays below the gas temperature, while the micro-diffusion flame is not ignited yet. Although the particles are not exchanging mass with the gas phase yet, the concentration of water is decreasing and the concentration of hydrogen is increasing already, due to diffusive mass transport between pre-heating and reaction zone. When the particle reaches the ignition temperature of 2350 K, the micro-diffusion flame, described by the point-particle model, forms and reaches temperatures above the bulk gas temperature. The particle starts to consume water and to release hydrogen and alumina, aluminum is not released in the lean case. Heat is transferred from the micro-diffusion flame to both particle and bulk gas, sustaining the heat transfer to the pre-heating zone for particle pre-heating as well as the evaporation heat required to sustain the homogeneous combustion. During combustion, the particle temperature T_p remains significantly below the gas-phase temperature because evaporative cooling restricts it to values below the boiling point of aluminum.

Figure 6: Flame structure of a steady, one-dimensional, lean, macroscopic flame in an aluminum-steam suspension. Inlet conditions: 100% H_2O at 450 K. Upper plot: temperature profiles of gas T_g , particle T_p , and micro-diffusion-flame T_f . Lower plot: Element mass fractions Y and flame standoff ratio.

Apart from these general observations, there is a strong coupling between the micro-diffusion-flames and the profiles of the macroscopic flame. The main parameter to the micro-diffusion-flame are the availability of oxidizer in the bulk gas and the bulk temperature. These boundary conditions differ substantially in lean and rich flames, leading to qualitative differences in the evolution of the individual particles and micro-diffusion flames traveling through the macroscopic flame.

Under lean conditions, generally sufficient oxidizer is available in the bulk. With the oxidizer partial pressure pushing the micro-diffusion-flame towards the particle, the flame standoff ratio

initially stabilizes relatively close to the particle within 2.5 particle diameters. As the oxidizer partial pressure decreases downstream in the macroscopic flame front, the FSR increases but stays at values below 10. Throughout the entire combustion phase, the particle temperature remains remarkably stable. The temperature of the micro-flame overshoots the gas temperature at ignition and slightly increases throughout the combustion phase. Once all Al is consumed, the combustion stops, marked with the dots in Fig. 6.

Only the remaining Al_2O_3 persists, which is inert and gradually heats up to the gas-phase temperature. This process draws heat from the surrounding gas, leading to a final dip in T_g .

Figure 7: Flame structure of a steady, one-dimensional, rich, macroscopic flame in an aluminum-steam suspension. Inlet conditions: 100 % H_2O at 450 K. Upper plot: temperature profiles of gas T_g , particle T_p , and micro-diffusion-flame T_f . Lower plot: Element mass fractions Y and flame standoff ratio.

Under rich conditions, the oxidizer mass fraction is already substantially reduced at the location where particle ignition takes place, as shown in Fig. 7. Still, the FSR initializes at values below 5, which is in range of the result from the lean flame and what is observed in single particle experiments [16, 22]. Also, T_f initially slightly overshoots the gas temperature, comparable to what is observed for the lean flames. However, the overshoot seems to be limited to the maximum bulk gas temperature, as similarly found for rich iron dust flames from theoretical considerations [47] and numerical simulations [9, 38].

As the particle travels downstream, the local combustion environment varies drastically, as already discussed in [9] for iron flames. As the oxidizer concentration in the bulk approaches zero, the micro-diffusion flame moves away from the particle, where no oxidizer is available, towards the bulk gas. This results in a sharp increase of the flame standoff ratio, which theoretically approaches infinity as $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \rightarrow 0$. This is a direct result of the model formulation. It is expected in a real flame that the micro-diffusion flame would either quench or transition into a group combustion regime, if a sufficient number of neighboring particles are present [37]. This is indicated in Fig. 7 by the disrupted line for the FSR. Appropriately, the micro-flame temperature T_f according to the Lagrangian model approaches the bulk gas temperature and converges towards a theoretical limit, as the depletion of oxidizer in the bulk prevents further combustion: The particle, which still contains unburned Al, has converged to a pure-evaporation state. Therefore, after the combustion phase, the inert evaporation phase follows as an additional phase which is not seen in lean macroscopic flames. In this phase, the particle model with theoretically $T_f = T_g$ and an undefined FSR provides the correct evaporative mass flux as would have been obtained from a single-layered evaporation model, yielding $\dot{m}_{\text{Al}} = 4\pi r_p \rho D \ln(1 + B_{\text{Al}})$, [17]. The particle temperature stabilizes on a new level, which is a steady evaporation state. This temperature is below the state with the micro-diffusion-flame, since the heat transfer to the particle is decreased. The gas phase temperature shows a visible slope as heat is taken from

the gas phase to sustain evaporation of Al. Finally, the remaining Al_2O_3 droplet is gradually heated to bulk gas phase temperature.

The evaporation of the excess aluminum in the inert evaporation phase produces aluminum fumes and most probably aluminum nanoparticles when cooled and condensed in a downstream turbine or cyclone. Therefore, in an energy cycle application where (aluminum) nanoparticles are generally undesired, excess aluminum or rich flame configurations must be avoided. However, in complex flame scenarios, regions with low oxidizer availability can even emerge in globally lean configurations due to localized oxidizer depletion, which would then lead to aluminum evaporation without combustion and fume formation. This underscores the importance of simulating realistic burner configurations and their local combustion environments to enable aluminum–steam combustion with minimal nanoparticle formation in future applications. The comparison between a generic rich and a lean flame configuration clearly demonstrates how differently the individual particles and micro-diffusion-flames evolve dependent on the combustion setup. To date, it remains to be explored how the qualitatively distinct temperatures and flame standoff ratios of micro-diffusion flames influence the formation, aggregation, and deposition of Al_2O_3 . There is a strong need for advanced point-particle models that incorporate key characteristics of the micro-flame structure to address these open questions. The development of these models depends on information from boundary layer resolved simulations as well as single particle and group combustion experiments. The oxidizer availability in flames is much lower than in typical single particle combustion studies, while the bulk temperature is typically much higher. Hence, experiments in hot ($> 2000\text{ K}$), low-oxidizer ($< 50\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$) configurations are explicitly useful for model validation.

5 Conclusion

The mitigation of nanoparticle formation during aluminum combustion in steam requires an in-depth understanding of the coupling between the micro-diffusion-flame around individual particles and the macroscopic flame propagation through the suspension. In this work, an Euler-Lagrangian model for aluminum-steam combustion is presented, which includes a mechanistic description of the structure of the micro-diffusion-flame in the Lagrangian particle model. The separate evaluation of the diffusion rates of aluminum and steam in their respective diffusion layers allows to overcome the common unity Lewis assumption, applying the mixture-averaged diffusion model instead. In consequence, flame standoff ratios between 1.72 and 2.57 are obtained in setups derived from available experimental references. The relative difference between the numerical simulation with the model and the experimental reference values is between 4% and 31%, which is a substantial improvement compared to models based on the unity Lewis assumption. Single particle combustion times from the heuristic correlations by Beckstead [10] and Halter *et. al.* [14] are well matched for a wide range of particle diameters ($20\ \mu\text{m}$ - $100\ \mu\text{m}$) and steam concentrations (50% - 100%), but depend significantly on the ratio of Al_2O_3 which is deposited on the particle or transported to the bulk gas.

Numerical simulations of macroscopic flame propagation are conducted with the model, obtaining first estimates for reaction front speeds in aluminum-steam suspensions, ranging between $15\ \text{cms}^{-1}$ and $35\ \text{cms}^{-1}$ for $20\ \mu\text{m}$ particles in $450\ \text{K}$ steam. The macroscopic structure of flames is analyzed for different flame configurations and reveals strong inter-dependencies of the micro- and macro structures and the flame configuration. In lean flames, individual particles pass two combustion phases, heating and steady combustion, while in rich flames the phases are qualitatively different: heating, unsteady combustion, and evaporation of remaining aluminum. The flame standoff ratio is significantly higher for low oxidizer availability in the rich flame, highlighting the need for improved particle models which consider the Al_2O_3 nanoparticle dynamics and evaluate the Al_2O_3 deposition dependent on the local combustion environment in the suspension. Investigations on the effect of more complex macroscopic burner configurations, such as Bunsen flames or counterflow flames, are required to advance the understanding of scale-coupling in aluminum-steam combustion.

CRedit author contribution statement

J. Mich: Methodology (lead), Software (lead), Validation (lead), Investigation (lead), Visualization, Writing - Original Draft **J. V. Hennings de Lara:** Methodology (supporting), Software (supporting) **T. Hazenberg:** Validation (supporting), Investigation (supporting) **H. Nicolai:** Conceptualization (supporting), Project administration (equal), Supervision (equal) **C. Hasse:** Conceptualization (lead), Resources, Project administration (equal), Funding acquisition, Supervision (equal) **All authors:** Writing - Review & Editing

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary data

The processed, secondary data which is visualized by the plots in this work is accessible under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17793815>. Unprocessed, raw data is provided on request.

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